

Supplementary Figure 6: Synergistic cytotoxicity of NKG2A-edited NK cells and RIG-I stimulation is independent of donor/tumor KIR-matching.

(a) Cytotoxicity of NKG2A-edited primary NK cells with KIR match, or mismatch during 20 h of cocultures with A549 cells (n=5 donors with KIR match, and n=5 donors with KIR MM). (b) NKG2A and KIR surface expression measured by flow cytometry on NK cells used in the cocultures in Fig. 6b, c, and Sup. Fig. 6a (n=18 donors). (c) 20 h cytotoxicity of -CTRg electroporated NK cells, data from the cocultures in Fig. 6b, and Sup. Fig. 6a (n= 5 KIR match donors and 5 KIR MM donors for A549 and Capan-2 cell lines, n= 4 KIR match donors and 4 KIR MM donors for A-431), and Capan-2 and A549 cells (KIR2DL1). (e) Cytotoxicity of NK cells with a KIR MM for only the indicated KIR, and NK cells from donors with KIR matches, after 20 h cocultures with the indicated cell line. (f, g) HLA-E surface expression on target cells used in Fig. 6c, and NKG2A on NK cells with KIR matches and KIR MM, as measured in control wells from cocultures with A-431 (f, n= 8 for A-431 target cells, n=4 donors with KIR matches, and n=4 donors with KIR MM), and with Capan-2 (g, n= 9 for Capan-2 target cells, n=5 donors with KIR matches, and n=4 donors with KIR MM). Statistical comparisons were performed using two-way ANOVA with matched donors and Šidák's multiple comparisons test (a, b, c, e), or paired t test for surface expression of proteins (f, g). *p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, ***p < 0.005, ****p < 0.001.